

target CRM	Phosphate Rock	REE	Cu	Cu	Bi, Co	Si (Pb/Zn as by-product)	Cu (Ag and Au as by-product)	Sb	In (as by-product of Au or Pb/Zn)	Ba (In, Ga, Co, Sb as by-products)	Mn	Ti		
application/waste flow	Different mining waste sites of LKAB, Sweden (Kiruna, Malmberget, Grängesberg), age 120 years	Different mining waste sites of LKAB, Sweden (Kiruna, Malmberget, Grängesberg), age 120 years	Different historical mining waste sites in Sweden	Mining waste site Håkansboda, Sweden, age 700 years	Mining waste site Håkansboda, Sweden, age 700 years	Mining waste site Laisvall, Sweden, deposited between 1940-2002	Bor (Field 1 and Field 2) tailings in Serbia, deposited between 1933-2003 during operation of old concentration plant at RTB Bor	Historical tailings in Balkan region (Lojane, Macedonia, possibly Zračica, Serbia and Gornje polje III, Kosovo)	Historical tailings in Balkan region (Probitip i and Veles, North Macedonia; Lece, Serbia)	Bolnich tailings in Goslar, Germany, mining of about 1000 years until 1988, flotation residuals processed between 1936-1988	Mining waste site Chvoletica, Czech Republic, deposited between 1951-1975 (Euro Manganese Project)	Mining waste site Otanmäki in Finland, tailings facility, deposited between 1953-1985 (Ilmenite Project)		
Treatment scenario without CRM recovery	Tailings from iron ore mining in tailing ponds	Tailings from iron ore mining in tailing ponds	Waste rock heaps	Waste rock heaps	Waste rock heaps	Tailings from lead-zinc mining in tailing ponds	Tailing ponds	Tailing ponds	Tailing ponds	Tailing ponds	Tailings from pyrite mining in tailing ponds	Tailing ponds		
(Partially) existing or potential treatment scenario with CRM recovery	Apatite will be concentrated and phosphoric acid subsequently recovered in a hydrometallurgical process (LKAB, n.d.). Methodology has been developed, planned start of production within the next couple of years.	Apatite will be concentrated and REE subsequently recovered in a hydrometallurgical process (LKAB, n.d.). Methodology has been developed, planned start of production within the next couple of years.	Needs to be explored	Needs to be explored	Needs to be explored	Needs to be explored	Needs to be explored	Needs to be explored	Needs to be explored	Recovery via different processes including flotation, hydrometallurgy and (bio)leaching.	Mn recovery via acid leaching of magnetic concentrate followed by electrowinning (Tetra Tech, 2022)	Ilmenite recovery (FeTiO3) via sieving, gravitational and magnetic processing. Methodology has been developed, planned start of production within the next couple of years.		
Nb.	Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?												
design/input-specific criteria														
1.1	Dispersion and heterogeneity in product/waste flow (accumulation and mass fraction within a product/waste flow)	How dissipated is the CRM and/or the CRM containing application in the product? Is the CRM and/or CRM containing application accumulated in specific components? Is the CRM accumulated/enriched in parts of the waste flow or is it more widely distributed within the waste flow? How is the CRM mass fraction in relation to the ore grade (in the application/component/product/parts of the waste flow)?												
1.2	Change in product design/input (changes in quantities, replacements, etc.)	What are the current developments regarding change in product design, especially change in CRM quantities and replacements? Are there expected input changes that will affect the waste flow?												
1.3	Product information and labelling (identifiability of CRM containing applications and components)	Does the product labelling provide sufficient information about the mass fraction and location of CRM in the product? Is there a required or voluntary labelling?												
waste flow-specific criteria														
2.1	Dispersion in waste flow	How high is the mass fraction of the CRM in the (collected) waste flow (in relation to the ore grade)? How is the CRM containing application collected (e.g. application-, component-, product-level, mixed with other products)? Is there a pre-sorting of components or products? Is there a pre-sorting regarding input material/parts of the waste flow?	Phosphate rock in the mining waste site has a similar ore grade to the primary deposit (4-8% apatite, 0.3-2.6% phosphite) since it was not recovered before. The grade can be even higher, because the main commodity, in this case iron ore, has been removed. The grade needs to be explored in detail but it is probable that parts of the waste are rich enough to contribute substantially to the need of P in Europe.	REE in the mining waste site has a similar ore grade to primary deposit (1200-1500 ppm) since it was not recovered before. The grade can be even higher, because the main commodity, in this case iron ore, has been removed. The grade needs to be explored in detail but it is probable that parts of the waste are rich enough to contribute substantially to the need of REE in Europe.	Average Cu grade in the waste rock heaps 0.1%-0.3%.	Cu grade is 6332 ppm (average)	Bi grade is 77 ppm (average), Co has an average grade of 315 ppm with elevated levels above 0.1%.	High grade, 92-98% SiO2	Main identified commodities are Cu, Au and Ag, with average grades of 0.023%, 0.36 ppm and 1.4 ppm respectively. These concentrations are below primary mean ore grades, however Au and Cu are somewhere within the same range (CRMs fact sheets, 2023).	Main identified commodity is Sb with an average grade of 1.2% in Lojane indicated in literature. Most important Sb deposits contain 0.1-25% Sb2S3 (0.07-18% Sb) (CRMs fact sheets, 2023). Therefore, the tailings in Lojane are in the lower range of primary extraction grades.	Pb and Zn are the main identified commodities at all locations. Literature data indicate the content of about 13 ppm in Probitip I, 6.7 ppm in Veles and 17 ppm in Lece. It occurs as impurity and could possibly be extracted as a by-product during extraction of main commodities (i.e. Au in the case of Lece and Pb/Zn in the case of Probitip I and Veles).	Research of the Bolnich tailing site is taking place for many years and is indicating about 14.5% Ba as sulphate, and 1.39% Zn, 1.21% Pb, 12.6% Fe, 0.15% Cu as sulphides. Sulphides are also containing Ag, Au, In, Co, Sb and Ga. Ga is also associated in silicates. The main components of the tailings are silicates (33.3%), sulphates (24.6%), carbonates (22.7%) and sulphides (19.3%) (Römer, 2019; Azevedo Schueler et al., 2025). Concentrations of the primary target in mining waste are typically lower than ore grade. Some trace elements could be enriched due to the processing. However, the accessibility (mineralogy, very fine grain size) might be still an issue.	Mn concentration is around 7.4% which is below primary mean ore grade (Euro Manganese Project, 2025). Mn primary mean ore grade varies between 10 and 50% (CRMs fact sheets, 2023).	Otanmäki tailings have a mass of 9.8 Mt including 16 % of ilmenite (FeTiO3).
2.2	Mineralogical state	In which mineralogical state is the CRM in the application or waste flow (e.g. metal, oxide, etc.)?	Apatite or phosphite	Apatite	Sulphide	Sulphide	Native	Sandstone, quartz, SiO2	According to XRD main phases are quartz (56-68%), kaolinite (probably dickite; between 23-31%) and pyrite (6-10%). Identified Au and Cu levels could be positively correlated with quartz and pyrite content, which might indicate that both commodities are present in both mineral phases. Optical microscopy identified the presence of limonite (<1%), rutile and leucosene (<1%) and traces of enargite, covellite, digenite, tetrahedrite, chalcocite, chalcocite, native Au, magnetite, hematite and cassiterite.	Main Sb mineral in Lojane is antimonicite	in is most commonly occurring as impurity in Zn ore (sphalerite)	Sulphates (Ba) and sulphides for by-products (In, Ga, Co, Sb)	The tailings consist of sandy to fine greyish material containing approximately 7.4% Mn, mostly occurring as rhodochrosite and kutnohorite; two mineral forms of manganese carbonate (Euro Manganese Project, 2025).	Ilmenite (FeTiO3)
2.3	Product and/or component collection (collection and return rates)	How high are the collection and return rates? Why are they high/low?	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
2.4	Current waste generated	Which waste quantities are currently generated?	Waste from apatite iron ore mining in Sweden is in the order of 20 Mt/year. However, there are probably about 1 billion t of historical waste. The potential is at least 400 kt/year P2O5.	Waste from apatite iron ore mining in Sweden is in the order of 20 Mt/year. However, there are probably about 1 billion t of historical waste. It is the largest REE deposit in Europe. The potential is at least 10-15 kt/year REE.	Different historical waste sites, in total 26 Mt waste rock with 67 kt Cu. Currently there is about 40 Mt of waste generated per year. Most if not all of this waste has very low levels of raw materials.	Håkansboda resource is about 250 kt in total with a potential resource of 1580 t Cu.	Håkansboda resource is about 250 kt in total with a potential resource of 19 t Bi and 78 t Co.	60 Mt of historical tailings in tailing dams	Field 1 contains 23.8 Mt of tailing material, while Field 2 contains 9.97 Mt. Research showed that Bor tailings are relatively rich in metals in field 1 (according to the latest estimations it contains 54,740 t of Cu, 4 t of Au and 33 t of Ag). It was also shown that Field 2 is low-grade material.	The mass of historical tailings in Lojane is estimated to 0.5 Mt. First rough estimations for Lojane tailings are 6 kt of Sb. The potential of Sb recovery from tailings is low, because the tailings are relatively small.	The mass of historical tailings is estimated to 7 Mt in Probitip I, 1.8 Mt in Veles and 2.7 Mt in Lece. First rough estimations for Probitip I tailings are 89 t of In, for Veles 120 t of In and for Lece 46 t of In.	Around 7 Mt of historical tailings from froth flotation, 44 t In, 170 t Ga, 1220 t Co (REWITA, n.d.).	Mineral reserve estimate: 26,644 kt + 27 Mt Mineral resource estimate: 26,960 kt + 27 Mt (Euro Manganese Project, 2025)	Historical tailings Interim resource estimate: 9.8 Mt of tailings including 16 % of ilmenite (FeTiO3)
2.5	Future waste generated	Which waste quantities are expected to be generated in the future?	20 Mt/year	20 Mt/year	Not applicable - closed/historical mining waste site. Waste of recovery operations needs to be disposed again.	Not applicable - closed/historical mining waste site. Waste of recovery operations needs to be disposed again.	Not applicable - closed/historical mining waste site. Waste of recovery operations needs to be disposed again.	Not applicable - closed/historical mining waste site. Waste of recovery operations needs to be disposed again.	Not applicable - closed/historical mining waste site. Waste of recovery operations needs to be disposed again.	Not applicable - closed/historical mining waste site. Waste of recovery operations needs to be disposed again.	Not applicable - closed/historical mining waste site. Waste of recovery operations needs to be disposed again.	Not applicable - closed/historical mining waste site. Waste of recovery operations needs to be disposed again.	Not applicable - closed/historical mining waste site. Waste of recovery operations needs to be disposed again.	
technical criteria														
3.1	Availability of identification technology for CRM containing application/material/component/product	Is there a technology to identify the CRM containing application/component/product to enable its recovery?	Classic sampling methods in mining sector: Surface sampling, boreholes, chemical and mineralogical analysis.	Classic sampling methods in mining sector: Surface sampling, boreholes, chemical and mineralogical analysis.	Classic sampling methods in mining sector: Surface sampling, boreholes, chemical and mineralogical analysis.	Classic sampling methods in mining sector: Surface sampling, boreholes, chemical and mineralogical analysis.	Classic sampling methods in mining sector: Surface sampling, boreholes, chemical and mineralogical analysis.	Classic sampling methods in mining sector: Surface sampling, boreholes, chemical and mineralogical analysis.	CRM quantities were assessed by drilling and sampling, sample analysis was done by ICP-MS.	CRM quantities were assessed by sampling and analysis, however only surface samples and samples in shallow holes were used.	CRM quantities were assessed by sampling and analysis, however only surface samples and samples in shallow holes were used.	Classic sampling methods in mining sector: Surface sampling, boreholes, chemical and mineralogical analysis.	CRM quantities were assessed in different drilling and sampling campaigns (Euro Manganese Project, 2025).	Classic sampling methods in mining sector: Surface sampling, boreholes, chemical and mineralogical analysis.
3.2	Manual removability of CRM containing application/material/component (selective removal)	Is it possible to manually remove the CRM containing application or material from the product/waste flow (is it screwed, glued, welded)?	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable
3.3	Automated removability of CRM containing application/material/components (selective removal)	Are processes available to remove the CRM containing application/component by automation? What is its TRL level?	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable
3.4	Identifiability and separability of CRM containing material after liberation	Is it possible to identify and sort the CRM containing materials after liberation (e.g. shredding)? This can be without preceding removal/sorting or after preceding removal.	No, fine-grained tailings material	No, fine-grained tailings material	Not tested	In sorting tests, the Cu content could be increased to 0.6%	In sorting tests, the Cu content could be increased to 0.6%	Under development	No, fine-grained tailings material	No, fine-grained tailings material	No, fine-grained tailings material	No, fine-grained tailings material	No, fine-grained tailings material	No, fine-grained tailings material
3.5	Ability to concentrate CRM containing material / mechanically remove impurities	Is it possible to concentrate or to mechanically remove impurities from the CRM containing material flow?	Yes, apatite can be concentrated	Yes, apatite can be concentrated	It might be possible by using mineral separation methods, i.e. flotation.	It might be possible by using mineral separation methods, i.e. flotation.	It might be possible by using mineral separation methods, i.e. flotation.	Under development	It might be possible by using mineral separation methods, i.e. flotation.	It might be possible by using mineral separation methods, i.e. flotation.	It might be possible by using mineral separation methods, i.e. flotation.	Using mineral separation methods, i.e. flotation, but will not reach required purity without subsequent hydrometallurgical processes (REMINTA, n.d.).	Magnetic separation is used to produce a magnetic Mn concentrate which is then leached to remove impurities (Tetra Tech, 2022).	Ilmenite concentration via sieving, gravitational and magnetic processing.

target CRM	Phosphate Rock	REE	Cu	Cu	Bi, Co	Si	Cu	Sb	In	Ba	Mn	Ti	
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Treatment scenario without CRM recovery	Tailings from iron ore mining in tailing ponds	Tailings from iron ore mining in tailing ponds	Waste rock heaps	Waste rock heaps	Waste rock heaps	Tailings from lead-zinc mining in tailing ponds	Tailing ponds	Tailing ponds	Tailing ponds	Tailing ponds	Tailings from pyrite mining in tailing ponds	Tailing ponds	
(Partially) existing or potential treatment scenario with CRM recovery	Apatite will be concentrated and phosphoric acid subsequently recovered in a hydrometallurgical process (LKAB, n.d.). Methodology has been developed, planned start of production within the next couple of years.	Apatite will be concentrated and REE subsequently recovered in a hydrometallurgical process (LKAB, n.d.). Methodology has been developed, planned start of production within the next couple of years.	Needs to be explored	Needs to be explored	Recovery via acid leaching of magnetic flotation, hydrometallurgy and (bio)leaching.	Mn recovery via acid leaching of magnetic concentrate followed by electrowinning (Tetra Tech, 2022)	Ilmenite recovery (FeTiO ₃) via sieving, gravitational and magnetic processing. Methodology has been developed, planned start of production within the next couple of years.						
Nb.	Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?											
3.6	Ability to thermally and/or chemically separate and refine CRMs from concentrates	Is there a thermal and/or chemical recovery technology for the CRM? What is its TRL level?											
		Phosphoric acid can be recovered in a hydrometallurgical process.	REE can be recovered in a hydrometallurgical process.	Potential separation by chemical or electrochemical means	Potential separation by chemical or electrochemical means	Potential separation by chemical or electrochemical means	Under development	The technology for extracting Cu, Au, and Ag has already been tested under laboratory conditions, and it was determined that the most optimal process for extracting these metals would be a hydrometallurgical process. TRL-4 hydrometallurgical process is proposed.	Potential separation by chemical or electrochemical means	Potential separation by chemical or electrochemical means	Hydrometallurgical separation and (bio)leaching (REMINTA, n.d.), TLR is TRL 6 or higher. Sequential extraction would be required to extract Ba first before the flotation process for elements like In, Ga, Co, Sb (Romer, 2019).	Mn electrowinning with different pre-treatment steps, TRL 8 or higher (Tetra Tech, 2022). This project has been classified as E1.2 FL3 G1 according to UNFC.	Not applied/outsourced
economic criteria													
4.1	Market and quality of 2CRM	Is there a market for the 2CRM? What is the quality of the 2CRM compared to the primary one? How volatile is the market?											
		Yes, no difference to primary	Yes, no difference to primary	Yes, no difference to primary	Yes, no difference to primary	Yes, no difference to primary	Yes, no difference to primary	Yes, no difference to primary. Besides Cu, also Ag and Au would be extracted as by-products.	Yes, no difference to primary	Yes, no difference to primary	Yes, no difference to primary. However, depends on the degree of processing.	Yes, the project will produce two high purity products: High Purity Manganese Sulphate Monohydrate (HPMSM) and High Purity Electrolytic Manganese Metal (HPMEM) (Euro Manganese Project, 2025).	Yes, no difference to primary
4.2	Price competition of 2CRM with primary	Would it be cheaper to use the waste flow instead of an ore to recover the CRM? Are there other materials or elements driving the recovery?											
		Similar costs	Similar costs	Unknown. Economical assessment is needed, but most likely not economically viable	Similar costs	Similar costs	Unknown. Economical assessment is needed.	Unknown. Economical assessment is needed.	Unknown. Economical assessment is needed.	Unknown. Economical assessment is needed.	No, but it may pay for some of the rehabilitation costs. Economic assessment is pending.	Refer to OPEX-CAPEX published by Euro Manganese Project (Euro Manganese Project, 2025).	Similar costs
4.3	Economic incentives	Do specific economic incentives exist (tax related, fees, etc.) to recover the CRM? Are there other materials or elements driving the recovery?											
		No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
4.4	Economically viable case studies	Are there (potentially) economically viable case studies for the recovery of the CRM? Does the value or the quantity of the CRM play a decisive role?											
		Kiruna, Grängesberg	Kiruna, Grängesberg	No	Needs to be explored, probably only economically viable together with either primary mining nearby or clean-up operation.	Needs to be explored, probably only economically viable together with either primary mining nearby or clean-up operation.	Needs to be explored	Needs to be explored	Needs to be explored	Needs to be explored	There were two case studies - REMINTA and REWITA, but economic viability was not proven yet (REMINTA, n.d.).	Euro Manganese Project (expected start of production in 2027)	Otonmäki Mine Ilmenite Project is in the feasibility phase and planned start of production is within the next couple of years.
4.5	Recycling conflicts with other materials or elements (especially more valuable ones)	Is there a recycling conflict with other materials or elements, especially with more valuable ones in the product/waste flow?											
		No	No	Depends on site	No, extraction of multiple commodities like Zn, Ag, Au, Co, Bi, and Sb.	No, extraction of multiple commodities like Zn, Ag, Au, Co, Bi, and Sb.	No, might be supported by other commodities like Ag or Pb/Zn.	No, Ag and Au as by-product; remaining material could be used for manufacturing of construction materials.	No, Ni, Co and Cr as potential by-products; remaining material could be used for manufacturing of construction materials.	No, by-product of other commodities like Au and Pb/Zn; remaining material could be used for manufacturing of construction materials.	No, fine fraction could be used in cement and concrete production or landfill. However, that fraction is rich in CRMs.	No	No, coarse fraction can be also used in construction
environmental criteria													
5.1	Logistics and infrastructure	How are the logistic and infrastructure requirements for the recovery process (process steps, distances, etc.)? Can existing infrastructure be used?											
		Next to primary mining operations, already existing processing sites. Shipping and railway infrastructure available.	Next to primary mining operations, already existing processing sites. Shipping and railway infrastructure available.	Depends on site	Need for nearby concentration plant, sorting and pre-concentration already in place, potentially also processing plant.	Need for nearby concentration plant, sorting and pre-concentration already in place, potentially also processing plant.	Closed/historical mining site. Logistics and infrastructure might be available (access to electricity, water and transport). Expensive shipping.	Mining site is still active, primary production is still active, so logistics and infrastructure exist (processing plant and active tailing sites).	Closed/historical mining site. Logistics and infrastructure might be available (access to electricity, water and transport).	Closed/historical mining sites. Logistics and infrastructure might be available (access to electricity, water and transport). The exception is Lece mine, which is still active.	Need for nearby treatment plant. Closed/historical mining site. Logistics and infrastructure might be available (access to electricity, water and transport).	Closed/historical mining site. Logistics and infrastructure might be available (access to electricity, water and transport).	Need for new processing plant. Closed/historical mining site. Logistics and infrastructure might be available (access to electricity, water and transport).
5.2	Energy and chemical requirements for separation and sorting	What are the energy and chemical requirements for mechanical separation and sorting?											
		Energy requirements for concentration and transportation.	Energy requirements for concentration and transportation.	Depends on site	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Energy requirements for excavation, transportation, and possible crushing and grinding. Need for chemicals in flotation.	Not differentiated from chemical processes.	Energy requirements for concentration and transportation.
5.3	Energy and chemical requirements for thermal and/or chemical recovery	What are the energy and chemical requirements for thermal and/or (bio)chemical recovery in comparison with primary production?											
		Energy and chemicals for hydrometallurgical process.	Energy and chemicals for hydrometallurgical process.	Depends on site	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Cu, Au and Ag extraction requires chemicals for flotation, acids for digestion, electricity and other reagents.	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Sulfuric acid and residual acid from Mn electrowinning circuit. The Project is expected to consume approximately 490 GWh/year of base-load electrical energy.	No thermal or chemical processing needed.
5.4	Recycling conflicts with hazardous substances	Is there a recycling conflict with hazardous substances? Are there hazardous substances in the respective application/waste flow? Will there be hazardous substances liberated during the recovery process? Can the hazardous substances be contained adequately?											
		No	No	Depends on site	As needs to be recovered and stored. This would also reduce leaching of As.	As needs to be recovered and stored. This would also reduce leaching of As.	No	Unknown	Lojane contains large amounts of As	Unknown	Tailing material holds also some toxic heavy metals such as As, Cd, Pb.	Unknown	No
5.5	Environmental impacts	What are the environmental impacts of the 2CRM in comparison with the primary CRM? Is there any implemented/standardized calculation pathway for environmental impact assessment?											
		Environmental Impact Assessment is available for Kiruna. Environmental impact similar to primary mining.	Environmental Impact Assessment is available for Kiruna. Environmental impact similar to primary mining.	Closed remediated sites can be a barrier for recovery.	Environmental Impact Assessment not yet available for Håkansboda. Recovery may improve existing conditions of historical pollution.	Environmental Impact Assessment not yet available for Håkansboda. Recovery may improve existing conditions of historical pollution.	Recovery can improve existing conditions of historical pollution.	Environmental Impact Assessment not yet available for Bor tailings.	Unknown	Unknown	Recovery can improve existing conditions of historical pollution.	The Euro Manganese project will clean up the contaminated site and eliminate a longstanding source of water pollution. LCA by Miniro Ltd. (Euro Manganese Inc., 2022).	Environmental Impact Assessment not yet available for Otonmäki. Recovery may improve existing conditions of historical pollution.
legal criteria													
6.1	Recovery targets	Are there material or element specific recovery targets?											
		Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable
6.2	Removal requirements	Are there any removal requirements related to the CRM containing application?											
		No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Requirements to remove/recover certain parts of the tailings to reduce environmental risks.	No	No
6.3	Legal incentives	Are there any legal incentives for the recovery of the CRM such as special facilities in application, permission or registration processes?											
		If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, remediation requirements can act as enabler.	If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, remediation requirements can act as enabler.	If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, remediation requirements can act as enabler.	If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, remediation requirements can act as enabler.	If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, remediation requirements can act as enabler.	If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, remediation requirements can act as enabler.	If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, remediation requirements can act as enabler.	If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, remediation requirements can act as enabler.	If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, remediation requirements can act as enabler.	If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, remediation requirements can act as enabler.	If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, remediation requirements can act as enabler.	If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, remediation requirements can act as enabler.
6.4	End-of-waste criteria	Are there established end-of-waste criteria for 2CRM?											
		Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable

References mentioned in the table, for overarching references refer to the main report

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LKAB, n.d. Luossavaara-Kiirunavaara Aktiebolag (LKAB). <https://lkab.com/en/>

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Tetra Tech, 2022 Tetra Tech (2022), Public Report and Feasibility Study for the Chvalcevice Manganese Project, Czech Republic, July 27, 2022. https://cdn-api.markdigital.com/apiman-gateway/ASX/ass-research/1.0/file/2924-02568235-2A1398516?access_token=83ff96335c245a094df02a206a39f4

CRM Act (EU) 2024/1252 Regulation (EU) 2024/1252 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 April 2024 establishing a framework for ensuring a secure and sustainable supply of critical raw materials and amending Regulations (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1724 and (EU) 2019/1020

Abbreviations used

CRM Critical Raw Material
 REE Rare Earth Elements
 TRL Technology Readiness Level